

VChain: Establishing Trust Based on Verifiable Credential Chains

Thanasis G. Papaioannou
Dept. of Digital Industry Technologies
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece
Email: atpapaioannou@uoa.gr

Vaios Ritas
Dept. of Digital Industry Technologies
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece
Email: vritas@uoa.gr

Abstract—Verifiable credentials (VCs) appear as a promising solution for holders to prove to verifiers the possession of certain desirable qualities or characteristics in a trustworthy and privacy-aware manner. Currently, a VC is linked to very specific properties for which it is issued and its trustworthiness is associated to its root of trust. However, determining the trustworthiness of a digital entity, i.e., a user, a microservice, etc., on arbitrary properties cannot be currently done based on their existing VCs, even if such a derivation could be trivial in the physical world; e.g., the possession of a PhD diploma can safely infer the existence of a BSc degree, or the certified access to an organization subdomain should provide access to the domain that includes it. In this paper, we define and experimentally analyze three different algorithms, namely GSP-X, CAM and LPwE, while employ VCs of multiple holders to infer the trustworthiness of a specific entity to possess specific properties of interest within a certain context, e.g., the likelihood of a microservice to meet advertised qualities for which it possesses no VCs. With synthetic datasets of credential chains of varying degrees of noise and hidden credentials from the ground truth, we experimentally establish that CAM and LPwE can accurately infer additional information about an entity’s attributes or qualities even based on 50% and 60% of available ground truth, respectively. The algorithms, when properly parametrized, can be strict and accurate enough to perform even access control or authorization in various practical settings. Moreover, they are able to estimate a level of confidence on the possession of specific attributes based on the VCs available at the holder. Implementing one of the proposed algorithms within a blockchain smart contract can serve as a trust broker for assessing trust among microservices in open systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Verifiable credentials (VCs) are a promising technology for establishing trust and enabling secure and privacy-preserving interactions in decentralized systems. A VC [1] is a set of tamper-evident claims and metadata associated with a Decentralized Identity (DID) that cryptographically proves who issued it. Examples include digital employee identification cards, digital birth certificates, and digital educational certificates. Moreover, the subject of a DID can be virtually anything, e.g., a person, a microservice, a concept, etc.

Verifiability of a credential does not imply the truthfulness of claims encoded therein. Validation is the process by which verifiers apply business or other rules to evaluate the trustworthiness of different claims in different contexts

This work has been funded by the EU project NGI TrustChain (grant no. 1011093274).

Fig. 1: Example claims in VCs about a subject.

with checks, such as the trustworthiness of the issuer, the professional licensure status of the holder, the date of license renewal or revocation, the sub-qualifications of the subject, prior interaction of the holder and the entity with whom the holder is attempting to interact, etc. Moreover, while multiple trustworthy claims may be associated to a particular subject, it may be unclear whether to trust the subject or not for related claims or in different contexts. Also, the set of claims for a subject in a VC may be *incomplete*. For example, assume that in a specific VC there is a claim that a certain subject (i.e., service A) possesses ISO 9001 and in another VC there is a different claim that the service offers a latency smaller than 5 sec, as shown in Fig. 1. However, these VCs cannot be automatically employed for verifying that service A has 99.99% availability or low security vulnerability. In open systems [2], microservices may join and leave randomly and they may autonomously interact with others. There is a need for a trust model to monitor interactions among microservices and establish trust among them, so as to limit security threats and low-quality risks [3].

In this paper, we deal with the problem of assessing the possession of specific properties by a subject holding VCs. Different properties for a subject may need to be validated in different contexts. We define three different algorithms, namely GSP Extended (GSP-X), Co-Acquisition Matrix (CAM) and Label Propagation with Encirclement (LPwE), for deriving new properties for a subject based on the properties held by a certain population of entities. The chronological order of obtaining the various VCs is taken into account in GSP-X and CAM that aim to find a causal, correlation or dependency order among different properties, while new properties are inferred in LPwE based on their frequency of reaching nodes (i.e., individuals) when propagating among nodes that possess similar properties. Employing synthetic data with various degrees of noise and hidden VCs from a specific ground truth, we

experimentally establish that CAM and LPwE can accurately infer additional information about an entity’s attributes and qualities even based on 50% and 60% of the ground truth, respectively, while CAM is also the lightest in terms of computational complexity. However, note that LPwE does not require time-ordered credentials to operate. All three algorithms are parameterizable by a threshold that determines the strictness of the desired accuracy of the different algorithms. When the respective threshold for each algorithm is high, they can be employed in contexts where the importance of security is paramount, while a lower threshold may be employed when a property needs to be derived with some desired confidence level of trustworthiness. We also experimentally find the optimal parametrization of the different algorithms for different levels of noise and missing data in the credential population. In the context of open systems, our algorithms would allow microservices to establish initial trust levels by inferring trustworthiness on different properties, e.g., availability, latency, accuracy, security vulnerability, etc., based on the existing credentials of the microservices population anticipated so far. This functionality could be implemented in a blockchain smart contract serving as a decentralized trust broker.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: In Section II, we overview the related work. In Section III, we describe our proposed algorithms for discovering hidden credentials. In Section IV, we experimentally assess our algorithms against synthetic datasets of varying degrees of hidden credentials and noise. In Section V, we provide recommendations for the practical employment of the algorithms. Finally, in Section VI, we conclude our work and indicate some directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

To the best of our knowledge, the problem of establishing trust on a subject for new qualities, attributes or claims, based on verifiable credentials (VCs), has not been addressed before. We overview some related work on trust models based on credential chains [4]–[9], VCs [10], [11], trust propagation and negotiation in the web [12], [13] and reputation for services [14]–[16]. Note that existing works rely on hierarchical trust relationships, establishing trust through certification paths from trusted authorities, while our algorithms infer trust based on credential co-occurrence patterns and graph-based relationships among entities, deriving new credentials from existing ones. In [4], SPKI/SDSI 2.0 framework towards a decentralized Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) and access control system is proposed. In SPKI/SDSI 2.0, the process of credential chain discovery is key for establishing trust and authorization. Verifying the authorization of a user to access a resource involves tracing a chain of digital credentials (X.509 certificates) from the resource back to a trusted authority or source. Similarly to [4], the problem of X.509 certificate chain discovery is also dealt with in [5].

In the context of certification chains, in NIST terminology [6], a trust anchor is a certificate authority (CA) with trusted certificates containing public keys that serve as the root of

trust. A certification path is a chain of certificates from a trust anchor to the target entity requiring trust verification. The approach in [7] is based on the notion of delegation, whereby one entity gives some of its authority to other entities. An access control decision involves finding a delegation chain from the source of authority to the entity requesting access, similarly to a Role Based Access Control (RBAC) system. Also, CredChain [8] is a blockchain-based SSI platform that allows secure creation, sharing and verification of credentials among users. CredChain allows a user to request a credential from a registered issuer via a blockchain DApp and store the credential in his private wallet. Another blockchain-based approach, named CredTrust, to create a chain of credentials is described in [9]. Issuers of credentials in SSI are assumed to be official entities and are trusted by a governing authority. CredTrust, proposes a way to introduce new issuers into the system via a trust propagation method originating from an already trusted issuer. The issuers form a hierarchy and the number of levels the hierarchy may vary. To form a trust path for propagating issuer trust, CredTrust uses special VCs named Supporting Credentials (SC) which extend the generic credentials with additional fields.

In the area of VCs, the work in [10] combines decentralized identifiers (DIDs) and VCs to establish a secure and privacy-preserving access control scheme that enables only authorized entities to access and control devices or data in the Internet of Things (IoT). Blockchain technology is used for decentralization, data integrity, and traceability, while smart contracts enable automated authorization. In [11], they use blockchain technology and map VCs to access control policies via Verifiable Presentation (VP) requests and responses. Verification involves creating a VP linked to a policy, invoking a subset of credential attributes. Users prove possession of these attributes using Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs).

In the area of trust management in the web, the work in [12] provides a framework, namely TrustBuilder, for automated negotiation trust between parties, allowing for sensitive interactions to take place online. Parties can use many different strategies to negotiate trust, offering trade-offs between the length of the negotiation, the amount of extraneous information disclosed, and the computational effort expended. The authors in [13] propose an approach for trust inference by means of traversing all trust paths from a digital identity that wishes to infer trust in a specific context towards another digital identity by means of Path Algebra. Some notion of trust associativity is assumed in [13] and trust is calculated by means of concatenation (e.g., multiplication, etc.) of trust weights of the links in the various trust paths, while calculated trust values of different paths between two entities are aggregated (e.g., summation, etc.).

Reputation systems, while not directly discovering credentials, assess entity trustworthiness through social referrals, e.g., feedback, reviews, or ratings. The approach in [14] employs correlation information among various QoS metrics and reputation feedback that propagates among interacting services to establish trustworthiness of web services. The reputation

system proposed in [16] emphasizes on the unlinkability between the ratings and the raters and on the integrity of reputation using ZKP and blockchain smart contracts. The work in [15] aims to create measures to tackle the known attacks against reputation systems by using dual permissioned blockchains - one for sensitive data (identities, transactions) and one for public data (ratings, reviews). It also employs VCs to authenticate user identities and reviews.

III. DESCRIPTION OF ALGORITHMS

We define three algorithms that traverse credential chains to derive implied credentials with a number, as described below.

A. GSP Extended

Our first algorithm, referred to as *GSP Extended* (GSP-X), is related to the field of data mining and more specifically that of Sequential Pattern Mining (SPM). SPM algorithms analyze datasets where the data have chronological or sequential nature and they aim to discover frequent sequential item sets taking into account a minimum support threshold, which is the minimum percentage of transactions or records in the dataset that should contain an item sequence in order to consider it frequent. The SPM algorithm that has been selected for discovering these patterns in our case is GSP [17]. Our approach aims to construct chains of credentials based on the frequent item sets or patterns that are mined from a dataset.

In more detail, the first step of our method, is to utilize the GSP algorithm in order to mine frequent item sets. Frequent are considered the item sequences that appear in a specified percentage of the records. Next, for every frequent item sequence $s = \langle c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m \rangle$, our algorithm calculates a ratio, called *relative in-order support*, as follows:

$$risup(s) = \frac{support(s)}{support(c_1 \cap c_2 \cap \dots \cap c_m)}, \quad (1)$$

where:

- $support(s)$: refers to the number of records in which a frequent item set in s appears as subsequence with the same order among the items in each record, while the subsequence items are not necessarily consecutive.
- $support(c_1 \cap c_2 \cap \dots \cap c_m)$: refers to the number of records where all elements of a frequent item sequence appear as a subset of the elements of each of those records. In this case, the order of the elements does not matter.

If the calculated ratio for a frequent item set is above a specified threshold then the item set is classified as a “chain”. This is because the elements of this item set maintain a certain order throughout the range of the dataset’s records, indicating a strong correlation in their ordering. Next, the algorithm removes duplicate chains and subchains which are contained within larger chains so that the resulted set does not contain repeated or overlapping chains.

Each final chain represents a logical sequence of credentials and the order of credentials in such a chain, reflects the natural progression (i.e., dependency list, temporal order or causal order) from one credential to another, resembling a linked list. Aim of our algorithm is to detect such chains of credentials

where the position of a credential in the chain, indicates its hierarchy as a prerequisite for another.

Definition III.1. For VCs X, Y , we denote $X \prec Y$, if VC X is to the left of VC Y in a chain, which means that claim(s) in X is a subset, prerequisite or lower level claim(s) than those in Y .

This implies that someone who holds VC Y also holds VC X or meets the requirements to obtain it. Thus, the existence of the consideration of the “in order” ratio (defined in equation (1)) advances the GSP algorithm, to ensure that the elements of a set have a hierarchical relationship, that is they form a chain. If the threshold for this ratio is set to a high value, then the elements of a certain frequent item set are required to be in a specific order more consistently, so that this item set to be considered to form a chain. Also, to set the threshold close to (or exactly) 1 can be applied in cases of access control, as it indicates that the elements of a frequent item set (almost) always appear in a specific order. It should be noted that in our approach we assume that each item appears only once in each sequence of the dataset. The time complexity of the approach is $O(N)$, where N is the number of chains in the dataset. The storage complexity depends on the number of patterns, which can be exponential to M at the worst case, where M is the cardinality of the different labels in the dataset.

B. Co-Acquisition Matrix

Hereby, we introduce an algorithm, referred to as *Co-Acquisition Matrix* (CAM) that aims to create chains of credentials by examining the sequences of a dataset, taking into account the co-acquisition of every pair of credentials and the order between them. Co-acquisition means that two credentials co-exist at the same record of a dataset, i.e., in our context, they are linked to the same entity. The algorithm utilizes a co-acquisition matrix, which is a table where the frequency of occurrence for each of the two permutations between any pair of elements is recorded, as long as the pair of elements satisfies a minimum support in the population of credential chains. The rows and columns of the matrix correspond to the different credentials.

The algorithm iterates over the sequences of the dataset and counts the times where any two credentials are acquired together and the specific order of acquisition. For every pair of credentials two counts are calculated depending on which one of them precedes in the sequence in which they appear together. For example, for the credentials X and Y , the algorithm counts the number of records where X precedes Y , i.e., $X \rightarrow Y$ and separately the number of records where Y precedes X , i.e., $Y \rightarrow X$, and places them in the corresponding cells of the co-acquisition matrix. The resulting co-acquisition matrix forms the basis for subsequent analysis.

Subsequently, with the help of the co-acquisition matrix and for every permutation of each pair of credentials, the algorithm calculates the relative in-order support ratio of the support count of a permutation over the total number of the credential sequences where the elements of the pair co-exist, regardless of their order, i.e., $risup(A \rightarrow B)$. If this ratio is greater than

a specified threshold for a certain ordered pair $X \rightarrow Y$ of credentials, then this ordered pair of credentials represents a strong sequential relationship and is considered as a “chain link”, i.e., $X \prec Y$.

Next, the algorithm joins the various pairs of chain links to form longer chains. As a prerequisite to join two links is required that the last element of the first link is the first element of the second one. The process of joining shorter to longer chains continues iteratively by making use of the *transitivity property*, with the additional condition that the second chain must not contain elements of the first, except for the element that is the connection point. For example, if the following chains are present:

- 1) $c2 \prec c7 \prec c5$ 2) $c5 \prec c3 \prec c9$

then these two chains are joined into a longer one, i.e., $c2 \prec c7 \prec c5 \prec c3 \prec c9$.

Also, a credential chain is separately joined with as many chains as possible. For example, if the following chains are considered:

- 1) $c4 \prec c6$ 2) $c6 \prec c8$ 3) $c6 \prec c10$

then these chains are joined into longer ones, as follows:

$$c4 \prec c6 \prec c8 \text{ and } c4 \prec c6 \prec c10$$

The final step of the algorithm is to filter the resulted chains in order to remove the subchains. As with the previous algorithm, the order of the credentials in the final chains reflects the hierarchy or the natural progression from one credential to another and thus we are led to the same property, as defined in Definition III.1.

Similarly to the GSP-Extended algorithm, a higher threshold for the ratio given by equation (1) for an ordered pair of items makes the semantics of the chain-link dependencies stricter, i.e., a threshold close to 1 is employed when derived credentials for entities are employed in access control cases.

The time complexity of CAM is $O(NM)$ for the discovery of chain links through the co-acquisition matrix, where N is the size of the dataset and M is the cardinality of the different labels in the dataset. The space complexity of CAM is $O(M^2)$.

C. Label Propagation with Encirclement

This approach, referred to as *Label Propagation with Encirclement* (LPwE), differs from the previous methods as it aims to estimate whether a credential can be assigned to an entity (i.e., a user) based on the credentials owned and on the credentials held by other related entities. The Label Propagation algorithm is employed as a basis and then a novel approach is followed to calculate the probability that a user owns a credential. Users are represented as nodes in a graph, where edges among them are created based on a relatedness metric. Hereby, we employ the Jaccard similarity metric (i.e., set intersection over set union) calculated on the credential sets of users, however, other similarity metrics could also be considered. Moreover, a similarity threshold is employed for creating an edge. This means that any two nodes are connected only if they share at least a specific number of common credentials, according to the similarity threshold employed.

Each node of the graph has a set of credentials, which can be considered as labels. The algorithm consists of rounds in which every node propagates its labels to its neighbours and at the same time receives theirs. At the end of each round, each node updates its labels and the process continues until convergence which means that no more label updates occur. During the execution of the algorithm, each node records per round statistics on which labels have arrived to it and how many times each one of them. These statistics are employed in our approach to estimate the likelihood of a node to have a particular label. The first step to calculate this likelihood is to calculate an initial or raw score rs_l for each label l received by a node:

$$rs_l = \sum_{r=1}^n \frac{t_{r,l}}{d \times r}, \quad (2)$$

where $t_{r,l}$ is the number of times that a specific label l has arrived at the node in round r , d is the degree of the node, r is the round of the label propagation, and n is the total number of rounds until label convergence.

The next step to calculate the likelihood of a node to have a particular label is to normalize the initial score of each label the node has received by dividing it by the highest possible score that each label could have. This max score s_{\max} represents the ideal scenario where a label is received in each and every round and from all the edges of the node. s_{\max} is given by the following formula:

$$s_{\max} = \sum_{r=1}^n \frac{d}{d \times r} = \sum_{r=1}^n \frac{1}{r} = H_n, \quad (3)$$

where H_n is the n -th harmonic number. Taking into account the above two scores, the normalized or *final score* s_l of a label l is given by $s_l = rs_l / s_{\max}$.

The final score s_l of a label l depends on two factors: The distance of the source node and the degree of the receiver node. The greater the distance a label travels, the greater the attenuation in its effect. The more connections a node has, the less impact any single incoming label has. This results in a system where the labels from immediate neighbors have a higher score compared to labels from distant nodes.

The higher the final score of a label (or credential) is, the more likely it is that the user corresponding to the node owns that label or meets the conditions to obtain it. Maximum final score for a label is achieved in the case of *absolute encirclement*, as defined below.

Definition III.2. Absolute encirclement for a node regarding a label refers to the case where the node receives the specific label through all its immediate neighbors in each round of the process.

In general, the longer the path a label takes to reach the node the smaller its effect. However, when the label is received in every round from all the edges of the node, then the resulting final score of the label is 1. An example is illustrated in Fig. 2. If the red node receives a specific label at first round from the green nodes and the same label at the second round from the blue nodes, then the resulting final score for this label is 1.

Fig. 2: Absolute encirclement

Depending on the context, a threshold can be employed, based on which all of the labels that arrived at a node with a score higher than the specified threshold are included in the node’s label set. In access control cases, a threshold score close to 1 for considering a derived credential is expected to be more appropriate to diminish the probability of false positives. This is experimentally investigated in Section IV.

The time complexity of LPwE is $O(N^2)$, where N is the size of the dataset, while its space complexity is $O(NM)$, where M is the cardinality of the labels in the dataset.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

All three algorithms were implemented in Python. A synthetic dataset of verifiable credentials (VCs) has been employed for evaluating them, which was constructed as follows: (a) 10 credential chains of lengths from 2 to 11 with causal order have been considered as “ground truth”. For credentials c_i, c_j with subscripts i, j denoting the order of credentials in the chain, the order $i \prec j$ declares semantic dominance of c_j over c_i in the sense that the claims made by c_j trivially imply (or depend on) those of c_i . (b) 100 different credentials without any semantic overlap in claims with others have been considered, referred to as “miscellaneous”, unless otherwise specified. (c) A test dataset has been created for 100 identities, randomly choosing for each of them one credential chain from the ground truth and perturbing it by randomly removing credentials and adding a random number and kind of unrelated labels from the miscellaneous set. We vary the percentage of the ground truth in the experiments and the size of the miscellaneous set and observe the performance of each algorithm to discover the ground truth for different parameters.

Each of the proposed algorithms has a number of parameters that may affect its effectiveness. More specifically, the different parameters to be selected per algorithm are the following:

GSP-X algorithm

- Minimum support: refers to the minimum number of records where a sequence of elements must be present to be considered frequent.
- In order threshold: refers to the percentage resulting from the quotient of the number of records containing a specific arrangement of the elements X, Y (i.e., XY or YX) to the total number of records containing X, Y of the independent order.

CAM algorithm

- Minimum support: refers to the number of records in which two elements X, Y appear together regardless of arrangement and is equal to the sum of the frequency of the arrangement XY and the frequency of the arrangement YX.

- In order threshold: same as in the previous algorithm.

LPwE

- Similarity threshold: refers to the minimum value of Jaccard similarity above which the connection between two nodes can be made.
- Score threshold: refers to the minimum score that a label must achieve to be accepted.

In addition to these parameters, there are also the parameters of the synthetic datasets, such as the percentage of ground truth elements that a record (i.e., the set of credentials of a particular person) includes, the total number of miscellaneous unrelated credentials (i.e., the “noise” level), as well as the number of those inserted in a record, the length of the ground truth sequences and more. All these were considered together to form a broad perspective of the behaviour of the algorithms, which they were compared based on their optimal performance.

To compare the three algorithms, various metrics have been considered, from which Accuracy, F1 score and Execution Time have been finally selected. The selection of the specific metrics has been carried out through a comprehensive evaluation of the algorithms, covering aspects of both performance and efficiency. Given that the evaluation of the algorithms’ performance requires, the comparison of the sequences predicted by each algorithm with the ground truth the specific metrics were deemed as appropriate, since the accuracy clearly shows the degree to which an algorithm correctly predicts a sequence, while the F1 score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, is particularly useful in cases where false positives and false negatives are significant as in our case.

In general, accuracy indicates the percentage of correctly predicted elements, that is true positives and true negatives against the total number of predicted elements. In our case, however, the algorithms do not predict true negatives, which means that accuracy is the percentage of true positives against all predictions. Also for comparing sequences where the order of the elements is important, a predicted element that is actually present in the ground truth but is not in the correct order is counted among the false positives. Here, for the first two algorithms in which the order of the elements is important, this is not the case as the predictions made by the algorithms preserve the correct order of the elements. All experiments were executed at least five times and average values and confidence intervals are plotted for each different metric.

B. Results

We first evaluate the optimal achievable effectiveness of the defined algorithms to discover various fractions of missing credentials from the ground truth, having found their best respective parametrizations. As depicted in Fig. 3a, Fig. 3b, even for 60% missing credentials, the CAM algorithm is very effective being able to achieve accuracy and F1-score values higher than 0.7 and 0.8, respectively. Even more, when 50% or less of the credentials are missing, CAM achieves absolute accuracy and F1-score values, i.e., it successfully discovers all ground truth without any false credentials added. Thus,

Fig. 3: (a) Achievable (a) accuracy and (b) F1 score of algorithms with optimal parametrization.

CAM could be safely used for performing access control in such a scenario. LPwE also has high achievable effectiveness, which is notable given that no temporal ordering of credentials is taken into account in this algorithm. The rapid drop of accuracy to 0 when the percentage of available ground truth is 100% is normal, since for the records that include all the ground truth elements, there is nothing to be predicted. However, the achievable effectiveness of GSP-X is moderate, as it struggles with low percentages of ground truth elements. Nevertheless, its effectiveness increases as the credentials data set becomes more complete, achieving perfect accuracy when 90% of the ground-truth credentials are available. Moreover, we experimentally found the optimal relative in-order support (*risup*) and score thresholds for the GSP-X, CAM and LPwE algorithms with respect to the fraction of available ground truth in the dataset. On the one hand, we established that while the optimal choice of *risup* for GSP-X and CAM is not affected by the fraction of available ground truth in the dataset, lower minimum support values are required for fractions of ground truth below 50%. On the other hand, the optimal score threshold for LPwE is 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 for the same respective fractions of available ground truth in the dataset, while it remains 0.5 for higher fractions of ground truth.

Regarding the computational complexity of the algorithms for achieving their optimal effectiveness for deriving missing credentials, our results, obtained at a machine with 4-core i5-1135G7 2.4GHz CPU and 16GB RAM, are illustrated in Fig. 4. Evidently, CAM algorithm is very lightweight, as compared to GSP-X and LPwE, taking only a small fraction of their execution time regardless of the fraction of ground-truth credentials available. LPwE is consistently heavier than other algorithms for all fractions of available ground truth, which is reasonable due to the increased complexity of the graph operations that it performs. The GSP-X algorithm has low computational complexity that increases progressively as the available ground-truth elements increase in the records, which makes sense since more and larger patterns are detected.

Next, we experimentally investigate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithms for different values of their parameters, while keeping fixed the percentage of available ground-credentials at 80% and the size of the set of miscellaneous credentials at 100. We aim to discover insights for appropriately setting the parameters of the algorithms in practical contexts. We investigate the impact of the relative in-order support threshold and the minimum support to the accuracy

Fig. 4: Execution time of algorithms with parameters that maximize their inference effectiveness.

Fig. 5: GSP-X (a) accuracy and (b) F1 score for different algorithm parameters when there are 80% available ground-truth credentials.

of the GSP-X algorithm in Fig. 5a. As depicted therein, the highest impact to the accuracy of GSP-X originates from the minimum support for a credential chain to be considered significant. Specifically, for lower values of minimum support, the algorithm becomes more inclusive and its effectiveness increases. However, increasing minimum support threshold gradually diminishes the performance of GSP-X. Also, considering that ground-truth is 80% in this experiment, this means that the minimum support still has to be set below 0.04 in most practical settings, so that chains can be formed. The selection of the relative in-order support does not seem to be important for the effectiveness of the GSP-X algorithm except for the case when it is combined with minimum-support values of 0.02 or lower, when it is clearly beneficial to select relative in-order support threshold values higher than 0.08. Similar findings regarding the trends of parameters for GSP-X can be derived from Fig. 5b, i.e., lower support threshold values and higher relative in-order support threshold values for higher effectiveness.

Regarding the parametrization of the CAM algorithm, as shown in Fig. 6a, Fig. 6b, the accuracy and the F1 score of the algorithm are very high for minimum support value between 0.02 and 0.05 and they significantly deteriorate for thresholds outside this range. Thus, selecting enough pairs of credentials is important in order to form credentials chains and derive missing credentials for the different individuals, but if the algorithm becomes too inclusive, chains tend to contain more false credentials. Also, as depicted in Fig. 6a, Fig. 6b, the impact of the relative in-order support threshold does not appear to be significant for the effectiveness of CAM algorithm, except for the case of very low minimum support where a higher relative in-order support threshold should be used to increase effectiveness, as expected, so as to filter out the higher number of item pairs selected initially and the

Fig. 6: CAM (a) accuracy and (b) F1 score vs relative in-order support when there are 80% available ground-truth credentials.

Fig. 7: LPwE (a) accuracy and (b) F1 score for different algorithm parameters when there are 80% available ground-truth credentials.

higher corresponding credential chains that are formed.

Also, the impact of the different parameters for the effectiveness of the LPwE algorithm is shown in Fig. 7a, Fig. 7b. Similarly to the case of the minimum support threshold for the CAM algorithm, the score threshold should be selected within specific ranges to maximize the effectiveness of LPwE. For similarity index thresholds above 0.1, the range of the score threshold that improves LPwE effectiveness is between 0.7 and 0.9. When adjusting the similarity index that determines node connections, it is true that higher index values result in higher scores for miscellaneous “noisy” credentials, which may be then included in the predicted chains. To avoid this case, one could increase the value of the score threshold, but up to a point, because afterwards that would reduce the effectiveness of the algorithm due to the exclusion of elements belonging to the ground truth. Overall, it can be derived from Fig. 7a, Fig. 7b that a low similarity index threshold should be selected so that there is enough circulation of labels in the graph, while the score threshold should be relatively high, so that stricter screening is employed for the labels that reach a node.

Next, we experimentally assess the impact of noise to the effectiveness of the proposed algorithms. To this end, we vary the size of the set of miscellaneous (unrelated) credentials that are mixed with the ground truth in $\{65, 100, 300, 500, 1000\}$. Recall at this point that the size of the different credentials in the ground truth is 65. As depicted in Fig. 8a, the CAM algorithm, when optimally parameterized with respect to the relative in-order support threshold, achieves ideal effectiveness in all cases of different noise levels, thus demonstrating robustness against noise. The LPwE achieves very high accuracy for all different noise levels considered, thus presenting itself as a potentially reliable choice for credential discovery in cases that temporal ordering of credentials may not be available. On the contrary, the effectiveness of the GSP-X algorithm remains

Fig. 8: (a) Accuracy Score Comparison across noises. (b) F1 Comparison at Optimal Performance.

consistently below 70% on the average for the different noise values, while also demonstrating higher variation than the other algorithms considered. The same trends are present for the F1 score in Fig. 8b for all three algorithms. As shown in Fig. 8b, the CAM algorithm achieves ideal performance, in the absence of any error bars, thus showing high performance stability.

Finally, we experimentally investigate the variation of the optimal parameters for the three proposed algorithms with respect to noise in the dataset of credentials. Specifically, we find how the relative in-order support (*risup*) threshold for the GSP-X and the CAM, and the score threshold for the LPwE algorithm have to optimally be selected for the various noise levels. We now vary the size of the set of miscellaneous (unrelated) credentials (i.e., noise level) that are mixed with the ground truth in $\{12, 65, 100, 300, 500, 1000\}$, while the percentage of available ground-truth credentials is always equal to 70%. Note that when the number of redundant credentials is too small, as compared to the number of different credentials in the ground truth (i.e., 65), then these noisy credentials start appearing in the synthetic dataset far too often, thus forming fake credential chains or pairs that make harder the discovery of hidden credentials from the ground truth. As depicted in Fig. 9a, for a very short size of the noise set, i.e., the optimal *risup* threshold is 1 for the GSP-X algorithm, while for larger sizes of the noise set any value for the *risup* threshold gives equally high accuracy, yet lower than 0.7. Similar results are obtained for the optimal *risup* threshold of the CAM algorithm for the different sizes of the noise set, albeit with higher accuracy, as illustrated in Fig. 9b. Therefore, it has been established that the optimal *risup* threshold for the GSP-X and the CAM algorithm can be safely chosen close to 1. Note that choosing an *risup* threshold equal to 1, renders the GSP-X and CAM algorithms suitable (i.e., strict enough) for discovering credentials related to access control. However, different results have been found for the optimal score threshold of the LPwE algorithm with respect to the noise level, as shown in Fig. 9c. Specifically, the optimal score threshold increases with number of different credentials in the noisy set, yet it is found to be lower than 1.

V. PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

As experimentally found, the CAM algorithm can be very effective to discover hidden credentials when the available dataset contains temporally-ordered credentials, while the LPwE can be effective when such ordering is not available.

Fig. 9: (a) GSP-X Optimal *risup* Threshold vs noise for 70% Ground Truth. (b) CAM Optimal *risup* Threshold vs noise for 70% Ground Truth. (c) LPwE Optimal Score Threshold vs Noise for 70% Ground Truth.

Moreover, we experimentally found the optimal parametrization of the different algorithms for various available fractions of ground truth and redundant unrelated credentials in the dataset. Specifically, the relative in-order support (*risup*) threshold should be chosen close to 1 for CAM, while the most effective minimum support value is 0.02. For LPwE, while the similarity threshold should be 0.2, the score threshold should be chosen increasingly higher with the number of different credentials in the noisy set and the fraction of available ground truth. A particular dataset reflects the credentials available in a population of digital entities. An estimation of the size of the noisy set of credentials in the dataset can be performed by means of clustering with respect to the support values of the different credentials. The size of the cluster with lower support values can be a proxy of the size of the noisy set. Also, the fraction of the available ground truth in the dataset can be estimated based on the application context with a specific ground truth of credential dependencies given a small random sample of the dataset. Moreover, a certain *confidence* value can be assigned to the credential discovery process in different application contexts by the proposed algorithms by means of feedback from digital entities based on prior interaction with the various entities regarding the real possession of properties associated to their discovered credentials by the algorithms. The functionality of each of the proposed algorithms could be implemented as a blockchain smart contract that would operate as a trust broker for a fee. Alternatively, this functionality could be implemented by a trusted third party (or an oracle network) that would function as a Trust Oracle to assess the trustworthiness of arbitrary entities on different claims.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we dealt with the problem of trustworthiness assessment of digital entities, i.e., individuals, products, resources, microservices, etc., in various contexts in the presence of verifiable credentials (VCs). We modeled the problem as a credential-discovery one, based on sets of VCs in the digital wallets of a population of entities. We proposed three innovative different algorithms for discovering the potential derivation of credentials for entities, so that their trustworthiness can be estimated, namely GSP Extended (GSP-X), Co-Acquisition Matrix (CAM) and Label Propagation with Encirclement (LPwE). We experimentally evaluated our algorithms for credentials derivation against synthetic datasets adding to sets of ground truth varying levels of noise and removing different fractions of credentials from the ground

truth. As found by a series of experiments, the CAM algorithm when appropriately parametrized can achieve high accuracy in discovering hidden credentials of entities. LPwE is able to operate effectively on non-temporally ordered credentials. We also experimentally derived insights for the appropriate choice of the parameters of the various algorithms in various practical settings. In the context of open systems, the proposed algorithms allow microservices to autonomously and dynamically assess and infer the trustworthiness regarding different aspects of other microservices that they may interact with. As a future work, we intend to consider reputation values of issuers of VCs, or trust anchors in general, in the algorithms for the discovery of hidden credentials. Also, we intend to investigate the calculation of a specific trust metric based on the derived trust chains for an entity. Finally, we will study an adaptive policy for the optimal parametrization of the algorithms in practical settings.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Sporny, D. Longley, D. Chadwick, and O. Steele, "Verifiable credentials data model v2.0," w3C Working Draft, January 2024. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vc-data-model-2.0/>.
- [2] J. Fritzsche, J. Bogner, S. Wagner, and A. Zimmermann, "Microservices migration in industry: Intentions, strategies, and challenges?" in *IEEE IC3ME*, 2019, pp. 481–490.
- [3] Z. Lu, D. T. Delaney, and D. Lillis, "A survey on microservices trust models for open systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 28 840–28 855, 2023.
- [4] D. Clarke, J.-E. Elie, C. Ellison, M. Fredette, A. Morcos, and R. L. Rivest, "Certificate chain discovery in spki/sdsi," *J. Comput. Secur.*, vol. 9, no. 4, p. 285–322, February 2002.
- [5] Y. Elley, A. H. Anderson, S. Hanna, S. Mullan, R. J. Perlman, and S. Proctor, "Building certifications paths: Forward vs. reverse," in *NDSS*, 2001.
- [6] E. Barker, D. Branstad, and M. Smid, "A profile for u.s. federal cryptographic key management systems (ckms)," NIST special publication, 800-152, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.800-152>.
- [7] N. Li, W. H. Winsborough, and J. C. Mitchell, "Distributed credential chain discovery in trust management: Extended abstract," in *CCS*, ser. CCS. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2001, p. 156–165.
- [8] R. Mukta, J. Martens, H.-y. Paik, Q. Lu, and S. S. Kanhere, "Blockchain-based verifiable credential sharing with selective disclosure," in *IEEE TrustCom*, 2020.
- [9] R. Mukta, H.-Y. Paik, Q. Lu, and S. S. Kanhere, "Credtrust: Credential based issuer management for trust in self-sovereign identity," in *IEEE Blockchain*, 2022, pp. 334–339.
- [10] Y. Li, Y. Fu, Z. Du, and Z. Cai, "An access control scheme based on decentralized identifiers and verifiable credentials in iot," in *ICCSMT*, 2022, pp. 279–283.
- [11] R. Belchior, B. Putz, G. Pernul, M. Correia, A. Vasconcelos, and S. Guerreiro, "Ssibac: Self-sovereign identity based access control," in *IEEE TrustCom*, 2020.
- [12] T. Yu, M. Winslett, and K. E. Seamons, "Supporting structured credentials and sensitive policies through interoperable strategies for automated trust negotiation," *ACM Trans. Inf. Syst. Secur.*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 1–42, February 2003.
- [13] V. G. Bintzios, T. G. Papaioannou, and G. D. Stamoulis, "An effective approach for accurate estimation of trust of distant information sources in the semantic web," in *Proc. of IEEE ICPS SecPerU Workshop*, 2006.
- [14] M. Mehdi, N. Bouguila, and J. Bentahar, "Trust and reputation of web services through qos correlation lens," *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 968–981, 2016.
- [15] O. Doğan and H. Karacan, "A blockchain-based e-commerce reputation system built with verifiable credentials," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 47 080–47 097, 2023.
- [16] J. Arshad, M. A. Azad, A. Prince, J. Ali, and T. G. Papaioannou, "Reputable—a decentralized reputation system for blockchain-based ecosystems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 79 948–79 961, 2022.
- [17] R. Srikant and R. Agrawal, "Mining sequential patterns: Generalizations and performance improvements," in *EDBT*, 1996.